

Surface active components of glass forming melts identified by thermodynamic model

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ABSTRACT

The use of thermodynamic models, especially the thermodynamic model Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva (SVTDM) still has a wide application [1]. The glass composition proposed by us is derived from the needs of the glass industry. Using the FACT database [2] it is possible to find all the thermodynamic data needed to quantify the SVTDM.

In multi-component melts, there is a tendency to deistribute components so that the resulting surface energy is minimal. The substances that lower the surface tension concentrates in the surface layer of the melt. The surface tension enhancing components have a lower concentration in the surface layer than in the volume. E.g. oxides MgO, ZnO, BaO, ZrO₂, and Li₂O increase the surface tension of glass, however other oxides, especially K₂O, PbO a B₂O₃, decrease it [3].

A variety of methods are known for measuring the surface tension of liquid systems. The most reliable results can be obtained by analyzing the sessile and pendant drop profiles. The principle of the method lies in the regression analysis of the drop profile based on the numerical solution of the Laplace equation [4, 5].

The chemical composition of the studied glasses was designed as four compositional series. The glass batches were prepared from analytical grade purity oxides and carbonates. Glasses were melted in Pt crucible in superkanthal furnace at the temperature of 1600°C for two-three hours in ambient atmosphere. The chemical composition (Tab. 1) of studied glasses was analyzed by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (VARIAN - Vista MPX / ICP-OES). Sessile drops were prepared from the glass cubes of approximate (2×2×2) mm³ dimensions on glassy carbon plate (Fig. 1a) in the atmosphere of pure nitrogen. Pendant drops were obtained by melting of the T-shape glass samples suspended in the platinum wire ring (Fig. 1b). The drop profile was recorded by the CCD camera uEye (IDS Imaging Development Systems GmbH) and digitized using the Lucia[®] software (LIM, a.s., Prague).

The surface tension was determined over the temperature range 1250-1500°C by the sessile and pendant drop methods. The values of surface tension were obtained by the least squares method by minimization of the sum of squares of deviations between the experimental and calculated drop

profile. The calculated drop profile was obtained by the numerical integration of the Laplace equation using the experimental density values.

The ZnO component was identified as the surfactant based on the significant negative correlation of its amount with the surface tension value. The surface tension values obtained by the sessile drop method were in almost all cases little bit lower than those obtained by the pendant drop method. On the other hand the values are identical within the estimated standard deviation.

Table 1: *Glass composition in mole percent of oxides as analyzed.*

Glass	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	CaO	ZnO	ZrO ₂	SiO ₂
NKCZ1	7.64	7.36	8.61	-	0.95	75.44
NKCZ3	7.54	7.44	8.84	-	2.86	73.32
NKCZ5	7.74	6.89	9.97	-	5.12	70.28
NKCZ7	7.66	7.01	9.98	-	7.18	68.17
NKzZ1	7.45	7.41	-	10.08	0.98	74.08
NKzZ3	7.30	7.06	-	9.63	2.61	73.40
NKzZ5	7.66	7.13	-	10.92	5.22	69.07
NKzZ7	7.83	7.00	-	11.03	7.54	66.6
NCzZ1	13.51	-	4.80	4.58	0.89	76.22
NCzZ3	13.72	-	4.72	5.01	2.71	73.84
NCzZ5	15.78	-	5.13	5.58	5.42	68.09
NCzZ7	15.78	-	5.11	5.43	7.4	66.29
KCzZ1	-	15.81	5.03	5.27	1.01	72.88
KCzZ3	-	13.95	4.47	4.95	2.66	73.97
KCzZ5	-	13.64	4.97	5.48	5.20	70.72
KCzZ7	-	13.88	4.98	5.43	7.25	68.46

Keywords: Thermodynamic model, Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva, surface tension

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